

Separate terms of use, version February 2024

Definitions used in the document:

Unit: faculty or independent institute involved in research (HCAS, HILIFE, Luomus, Swedish School of Social Science)

Metadata: *Data describing, in compact form, datasets, including their content, structure, context, management, processing or compilation*

Curation of research data: *the processes to maintain, preserve and update research data throughout their life-cycle to ensure their continued integrity, availability and usability*

(<https://sanastot.suomi.fi/terminology/3bdbcac2-e57f-49c1-b104-e37eff042834/concept/0c68edb2-fe39-4ca7-9612-16aa57377ef1>)

In this document, **University** denotes the University of Helsinki.

Researcher(s) denotes person who are seeking storage space in the service.

About the service

1. The service is a repository for static datasets produced through research. The service is not intended as a processing or storage location at the active data processing stage.
2. The service is targeted at researchers of the University of Helsinki. Researchers can apply for storage space for their data in the service. Researchers and their data must comply with the general terms of use of the service. In addition, their units must support the storage of the data in the service.
3. Service users commit to complying with the terms of service when completing the service subscription form. In the subscription form, users provide information on the data they are submitting to the service, which are used to verify whether the data are fit for the service and whether the storage capacity of the service should be used to preserving the data. The order form also asks users to provide the necessary metadata for their data.
4. The service requires University of Helsinki credentials.
5. The service accepts data produced by University of Helsinki researchers or data to whose production University of Helsinki researchers have significantly contributed.
6. Datasets containing special categories of personal data cannot be accepted into the service.

Researchers' commitment

7. Researchers confirm that they have the right to submit the data to the service. In this document, 'right' means that
 - a. Researchers have collected the data independently or together with individuals who agree to the storage of the data in the service
 - b. Rights to the data have not been transferred exclusively to a third party
 - i. Examples of this would include a project collaboration agreement, commissioned research agreement or other agreement

- c. The right of use or other rights of a third party or researchers' obligation of secrecy does not preclude the material's storage in the service
8. Researchers confirm that
 - a. The data have been collected in accordance with applicable legislation (e.g., data protection legislation) and research ethics guidelines. For example, a data protection notice has been drawn up if personal data are processed.
 - b. The data contain no third-party trade secrets or other confidential information. (In other words, the use of the data is not restricted, for example, by a non-disclosure agreement, data transfer agreement, collaboration agreement or commissioned research agreement.)
 - c. The dataset contains no special categories of personal data, such as health data.
9. Researchers grant the University a parallel, permanent and free-of-charge access to the data. Researchers are responsible for obtaining the right to store and otherwise process the data.¹
10. Researchers can also grant the University the right to disclose the data from the service for other research purposes. If researchers do not grant the University the right of disclosure, the data cannot be disclosed from the service. If researchers grant the University the right to disclose the data, they also grant the right to edit the material.
11. In the case of data produced by several individuals, one individual files the request for storage on behalf of the group as a whole, confirming that the group has approved this. An [agreement template](#) is available for collecting the group's approval. In addition, coordinating researchers must confirm that they have done everything possible to reach all the owners of the data.
12. Researchers undertake to provide the metadata necessary for utilising the data and agree that the metadata will be openly published.

The role of units (faculties and independent institutes involved in research)

13. Unit-specific research committees or similar (by unit decision) decide, as part of the service process, which datasets can be stored and preserved under their quotas.

Administration of service capacity and erasure of preserved data

14. All datasets have one or more contact person and information on the unit of origin. If the contact persons cannot be reached, the unit will decide on the data and, if necessary, appoint a new contact person.
15. Researchers grant the University the right to erase the data from the service after the retention period has expired. The University has the right to decide independently how long it

¹ Depending on the type of research where the data have been collected and the related funding terms and agreements, researchers may have previously handed over proprietary rights or rights of use to the University. All such transfer agreements concluded previously between the University and researchers will continue to apply, and the terms of use of the service are not intended to reduce the proprietary rights or rights of use previously granted to the University. The terms of use of the service ensure that the University has sufficient rights to manage all data stored in the service.

Before accepting the terms of use of the service, researchers are obliged to ensure that the use of the data is not restricted by the rights of parties outside the University. The rights of external parties can be based, for example, on agreements concluded between the University or a researcher and a third party, or on their research collaboration. See sections 8, 9 and 12 of the policy of use.

will store data and when they will be erased. Before erasure, the contact person will be notified.

16. Data will be erased from the service manually as a result of the annual review. Contact persons or units will be notified before the erasure, in which case they can, for a legitimate reason, apply for an extension of the retention period. For particularly compelling reasons, data can be erased at other times, such as if problems related to data protection arise later or, for example, if it turns out that researchers have provided incorrect information.
17. In the curation of research data, files are not opened and checked, for example, with the help of checksums. Curation is limited to checking file formats in connection with the annual review so that the selected file formats support long-term preservation.
18. If they have valid University credentials, submitters of data can always access the data for as long as they are stored in the service.
19. If a third party questions the data submitter's right to the data, the University must investigate the claim and its grounds. The University has the right to prevent the data submitter from accessing the data during the investigation, as well as to make a final decision on preserving the data. The University is not responsible for any potential damage caused by the refusal of access.